

Digital assets and tools for circular value chains and manufacturing products

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Use Cases

Extending sustainable manufacturing and reparability approaches for aeronautic value chains

Eco-design, diagnosis and maintenance for modular mobile phones

R-cycles in material flows for warehouse design, construction and operation